

Finger actuation of a Modular Wearable Exoskeleton for Hand/Wrist Rehabilitation and Training

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Abstract—Robot rehabilitation is an emerging and promising topic that incorporates robotics with rehabilitation and neuroscience to define new methods for supporting patients with diseases. The rehabilitation process could increase the efficacy exploiting the potentialities of robot-mediated therapies. In this paper we describe the hand module of a system for hand/wrist motion training. The whole system is designed to be wearable, easy to control and manage. It can be used by the patient in collaboration with the therapist or autonomously. The paper introduces the main steps of device design and development and presents some possible exercises that can be performed by a user with limited wrist mobility.

Index Terms—exoskeleton, robotic rehabilitation, wearable robot

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, most of the people are living a longer and healthier life than in the past, as the mean age of the population increases, and, as a consequence, the overall social impact of chronic diseases related to the musculoskeletal and nervous system becomes more important. On the other hand, the spreading of technology in everyone everyday life is playing an important role in preserving and guaranteeing a high quality of life also in presence of temporary and/or permanent diseases.

Technology advancements in the medical and assistive field allow people with disabilities to have a life that in many cases is almost completely autonomous. Devices and supports can help in the autonomy of activities of daily living (ADLs), in communication, study, learning, and, more in general, in the whole process of integration.

In this general framework, the upper limbs have important role for all daily activities, but are often affected by chronic or temporary diseases, e.g. stroke. Various exoskeleton devices have been already developed as support tools for this part of the body [1]. In particular, different devices are specifically developed for the wrist, e.g. [2], [3] and for the hand, e.g. [4], [5]. Notwithstanding the technological developments and the evidence of clinical effectiveness of robotic technologies for upper-limb neuro-rehabilitation, there are still some limits

Fig. 1: (a) The differential-based system for finger coupling. (b) The overall hand/wrist exoskeleton system worn by a user.

in their diffusion [6]. Technological and economic barriers together with communication biases between the producers of the technologies are still open issues.

In this paper we focus on the hand module of an integrated exoskeleton for hand and wrist motion assessment and training (Fig. 1). The device has been designed starting from the user's point of view, to be easily and autonomously wearable, easy to control and manage, modular and versatile. The device can be used by the patient in collaboration with the therapist or autonomously, and is composed of two independent and modular elements: the wrist actuation and the hand actuation systems. In particular, we will briefly discuss the main design requirement and choices, we will present the developments that we proposed and some applications.

II. HAND EXOSKELETON: REQUIREMENTS

In this paper we focus in particular on the hand module of an integrated actuated hand/wrist exoskeleton, suitable for upper limb rehabilitation and training, usable both in specific rehabilitation spaces, e.g. clinic/rehabilitation centers and at home for people with long term impairments. It's worth to underline that the design process was user-centered: a potential user was involved from the first phases of the device. His contribution allowed to define a proper set of design requirements and he was also involved in the design and development phases.

A. Target application

The impairments and disabilities involve high variability in the available range of motion, muscle tone, joint stiffness, etc. Furthermore, even for the same disease, such characteristics vary according to severity, level and time since injury, subject's age, etc. [7]. For these reasons the definition of a comprehensive set of design guidelines for assistive and rehabilitation hand and upper limb exoskeletons is impossible. The device developed in this paper is designed for a specific application, namely as a rehabilitation and training for a subject with low residual force, low active control of the hand and the wrist, low spasticity, and low muscle tone. We developed the device for the needs and requirements of a representative user, but the modular structure of the proposed solution, as well as the particular kinematic structure of finger actuation system, makes it adaptable to different subjects and different needs.

B. Mechanical requirements for hand module

The goal of the proposed exoskeleton is to reproduce the opening/closing motion of the hand, which corresponds to a finger motion that includes mainly an extension/flexion motion and a more limited adduction/abduction motion. In summary, The hand module of the device is required to support the user in realizing flexion/extension motions of all the fingers, with an amplitude that can be varied in the whole physiological extension previously summarized. The fingers are requested to be controlled both independently and in a coordinated way. Adduction/abduction motion of the fingers is not controlled by the exoskeleton and neither constrained by its mechanical structure.

C. Requirements for wearability and adaptability

Initial users' feedback on preliminary versions of the device suggested that one of the main limits of these prototypes was that it was impossible for the user to wear them autonomously. One of the main and challenging requirements to be addressed is therefore providing the possibility, also for users with limited motion capabilities of the upper limb, to wear and use the device. Another important aspect that has been considered is the adaptability of the device to user's specific characteristics (i.e. anthropometric measurements). Regarding the hand part, to limit as much as possible any interference during ADLs, the mechanical transmission system has to be constrained to be on the back of the fingers and the palm, the width of the finger modules should not exceed too much the finger width. The weight of the exoskeleton should be as light as possible and the inertia should be distributed so as not to fatigue the patient. Hand exoskeleton structure and control have been developed so that each finger module can be used and controlled independently.

D. Independent and coupled finger actuation

Electric motors, i.e DC motors, brushless DC (BLDC) motors, servo motors and linear actuators are widely employed for hand exoskeletons [8]. The mechanical transmission from the motor to the finger joints is realised by means of articulated systems or tendons. Linear actuators are employed in some applications because they can apply bi-directional forces and

therefore can push or pull the mechanical linkage system to flex or extend the fingers [9]. Linear actuators that can be employed in this type of applications have quite small dimensions, so that one actuator per finger can be used. This kind of actuation has multiple advantages, for instance the independent finger actuation is possible and finger control is rather precise. The linear actuator and the sizes of the linkages in the articulated transmission system have to be defined to allow the patient to fully flex and extend the finger, and this requirement could lead to a solution that is bulky and difficult to wear [11].

In this context differential mechanisms can be employed to couple the actuation of two adjacent fingers, allowing to decrease the number of actuators, reducing the weight and the complexity of the system, and improving wearability. It's worth to notice that the differential mechanism does not rigidly connect the fingers, but maintains them independent, so if one of the two branches of the differential is blocked, the other one can still move.

III. DEVELOPMENT

A preliminary version of the wrist module was presented in [10], while the first solution for the hand actuation was presented in [11]. Such a solution, in particular, was modular at the finger level: each finger was actuated by a linear actuator, the actuators could be independently controlled or coordinated. The kinematic actuation system, that allowed to couple the metacarpo-phalangeal and proximal-interphalangeal motions, was developed on the basis of the first postural synergy. The drawback of such initial solution was its encumbrance, its stiffness and its limited adaptability to different users. The following studies were therefore devoted to improve such aspects, and in particular to develop a more versatile, lighter and adaptable actuation system for the finger modules. Such development is summarized in [9], where different finger actuation systems were analyzed and compared from the kinematic and mechanical points of view. To limit the number of actuators without constraining finger motions, a differential mechanism was developed (Fig. 1 (a), Fig. 3), the proposed solution is detailed in [12]. In particular, the differential system CAD model is detailed in Fig. 3. The overall modular hand/wrist system (Fig. 1 (b)), and its control system is detailed in [13], in such a work it's worth to mention the automatic closure system for the forearm support, that improved the overall wearability.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we presented the main features of a hand/wrist exoskeleton for rehabilitation and training, focusing in particular on the hand module. The device has been developed to enhance patient independence and autonomy in the rehabilitation and training phase, reducing the time and the efforts needed by a physiotherapist or an external trainer.

The system has been developed following a modular approach so that the user can personalize it according to her/his needs. Wrist and hand modules can be used jointly or independently, on the basis of user's needs. The hand module can be further divided at a finger level, and single fingers can be

Fig. 2: Simplification of the finger actuation system detailed in [9]. First row: hand actuation system (a) First solution, with fully constrained finger motion. (b) Second solution with improved adaptability. (c) Third solution with improved wearability and lightness. Second row, finger modules. (d) First solution. (e) Second solution. (f) Third solution.

Fig. 3: Independent (a) and coupled (b) finger actuation.

actuated. Also the GUI has been developed to manage single or multiple modules.

We also developed an actuation system for a hand finger exoskeleton in which the motion of two adjacent fingers is coupled by a differential mechanism. The developed gear-based differential mechanism homogeneously distributes actuator's force, while keeping independent the motion of the coupled fingers, so that if one of them is blocked because in contact with an obstacle, the other one is still able to move.

The reduction of the number of actuators is a significant advance for the device, since it is lighter, less complex, and with a lower energy consumption, therefore with a longer battery life cycle.

The device has also been tested in terms of compatibility with a simple and widely used tracking system with

Fig. 4: CAD model of the differential mechanism for coupling the motions of two adjacent fingers (a) exploded view, (b) assembled system.

low economic impact, such as the LeapMotion Controller to demonstrate that with the presented version of the exoskeleton it is not only possible to carry out physiotherapy tasks but also to record and monitor them remotely, thus allowing to expand the rehabilitation possibilities and opportunities for patients, doctors and physiotherapists.

The proposed device represents a useful tool in telerehabilitation, the possibility of loading personalized exercises and to record and replay an activity guided by the physiotherapist allows reducing the need of the face-to-face interaction between the patient and the physiotherapist.

The exoskeleton presented in this paper currently has TRL 4 (Technology Readiness Level) and its overall hardware structure is going to be further optimized in the next future. In a successive phase of the work, the hardware structure will be further enhanced, the objective is to allow a patient with limited arm and hand motion capabilities to assemble and disassemble the different modules and to wear them autonomously.

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